

Why do bad laws get adopted? The case of the anti-corruption law in Bulgaria.

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Abstract

This study explains the approval of the Anti-Corruption and Illegal Assets Forfeiture (ACIAF) Act in the Bulgarian Parliament despite the controversies entailed in this reform. This study unravels the black box of the policy process in Bulgaria and provides an overview of how laws are adopted, especially when personal interests are vested in them. By analyzing the policy process that spans from October 2017 to January 2018, it delineates the timing of key decisions and sees whether they took place informally outside of the public political stage. Thus, it sheds light on the personal motivations, party motivations, and expertise-based motivations that led to the creation of the legal mechanisms of the CACIAF.

Keywords

anti-corruption; legislature; political party; law-making; national assembly

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Introduction

Bulgaria is considered among the most corrupt members of the European Union and 90% of the Bulgarian public opinion holds that high levels of corruption are concentrated in the top echelons of power (Kukutschka, 2021: 11). This issue has entered public discourse abruptly, with the fall of the Iron Curtain, and it continues to receive a lot of attention today. Since 2005, the Bulgarian government has introduced several anti-corruption measures with the ambition to join the European Union and meet the Copenhagen criteria.² Although corruption levels have decreased, they remain among the highest in the EU and recent studies suggested corruption is on the rise again since 2011 (CSD, 2016: 11).

Following another recommendation of the European Commission to introduce strong anti-corruption measures and to establish a state agency tackling this issue, the Bulgarian government adopted in 2017 legislation that founded a new state agency, the Commission for Anti-Corruption and Illegal Assets Forfeiture (CACIAF) (*Komisiya za protivodeistvie na koruptsiyata i za otnemane na nezakonno pridobito imushtestvo*). The bill was proposed by the Council of Ministers, formed by the ruling coalition of the center-right party Citizens for European Development of Bulgaria (GERB) and the populist pro-Russian party United Patriots (OP). The bill was widely endorsed in the Parliament, not only by GERB and OP, but also by the Movement of Rights and Freedoms (DPS, the party representing the Turkish minority), and the small right-wing populist party *Volya*.³ The Bulgarian Socialist Party (BSP), the opposition, proposed a competing anti-corruption bill, but their proposal was met with hostility in the Parliament and it did not pass.

Three years after its founding, CACIAF did not yield any significant results as there are no convictions for high-level corruption cases in 2018 and 2019 (ACFF, 2020). In fact, in 2019 CACIAF was involved in a national scandal, called *Apartmentgate*, when it decided there was no evidence of high-ranking officials (including the chairman of the Commission itself - Plamen Georgiev) being involved in a conflict of interest by purchasing private property at prices below the market value.⁴ Due to such controversies, the opposition parties proposed in 2021 the suspension of CACIAF⁵, arguing that investigations have been selective, without a comprehensive standard for assets evaluation (OFFNews, 2019). Moreover, some CACIAF cases were identified as commissioned by the ruling elite against vocal opponents of the status quo (Bregov, 2017).⁶

² Examples include the Commission for Coordination of Anticorruption Action; the Commission for Establishment of Assets Acquired Through Criminal Activity and Administrative Violations; or the Strategy for Transparent Governance and for Prevention and Counteraction of Corruption for the Period 2006-2008.

³ The Parliament included: 95 deputies from GERB, 80 from BSP, 27 from OP, 26 from DPS, and 12 from *Volya*.

⁴ *Apartmentgate* erupted in the spring of 2019 and involved the purchase of property at prices lower than the market value by senior officials, including the former Minister of Justice and Chairwoman of the National Assembly - Tsetska Tsacheva, the former chairman of GERB - Tsvetan Tsvetanov, the former Minister of Culture and Education - Vezhdi Rashidov, the Deputy Minister of Youth and Sport - Vanya Koleva and the Deputy Minister of Energy, Environment and Water - Krasimir Parvanov (Kapital, 2020). CACIAF argued in a statement that the evidence provided was not enough to file a case to the state prosecution. An investigative report claims that CACIAF miscalculated the discrepancy between the incomes and the properties of the senior officials in order to stay below the confiscation threshold. For example, CACIAF undervalued the property of Tsvetan Tsvetanov, compared to independent estimations, by 381000 leva, the equivalent of about 196000 euros (Bivol, 2019).

⁵ The centre-right coalition of Democratic Bulgaria, which entered parliament in 2021 as an oppositional party to GERB, submitted twice a bill for the suspension of this agency.

⁶ CACIAF started the forfeiture of property of 500000 leva of the businessman Ivo Prokopiev, owner of the independent and critical of the government media group Capital (Radio Free Europe, 2020).

The adoption of such a questionable law/reform may not be unusual for an authoritarian state, such as Russia, or for a hybrid regime in which political participation is limited and the level of state capture is devastating, such as Nigeria. Bulgaria, however, as a member of the European Union, should strictly follow the European guidelines based on liberal democratic principles of establishing the rule of law, protecting human rights, and fostering economic development. The Bulgarian state has a pluralist institutional framework, mostly free and fair elections, and a multi-party system upholding the basic principles of political representation, association, and participation. Similarly to many of the post-communist states, parliamentarism was identified as the core framework of the newly created democratic system and, hence, the Bulgarian National Assembly represents ‘the central site of policy formulation and played a key role in shaping the post-communist order’ (Zubek, 2008: 147).

Considering that the institutional framework and international stakes are supposed to facilitate good governance, it is puzzling that the anti-corruption legislation took such questionable form. Moreover, it is perplexing why the bill passed nearly without amendments, given that its problematic parts have been loudly questioned by NGOs, by president Rumen Radev, and by other organizations. The law-making process is expected to produce good formal institutions, while the rent-seeking behavior is supposed to take other forms. Instead, the Bulgarian parliament produced a controversial body that is used *de facto* for repression of the opposition, without holding responsible those in the highest echelons of power.

Before proceeding further, it is crucial to establish the assumptions vested in this study and to justify why this law is conceptualized as *bad*. The Oxford Dictionary of Law defines the concept of law as the enforceable body of rules that govern society (Law, 2018). However, to evaluate the quality of a legal text, this study employs a definition based on legal philosophy such as a rule that is delineated by its internal morality, which is defined by its purpose to secure justice by reasonably resolving coordination problems for the common good of a given community (Dickson, 2009:162). There is less disagreement regarding the quality of a law when it fails to achieve its aims because it appears ineffective. This applies to the ACIAF Act, as since its establishment it has not brought about any hard sentences, nor did it severely punish a high public official.

Although the adjectives *good* and *bad* normally represent a value judgment based on personal experience (Reed, 2010: 903), a concept of a *bad* law exists in legal philosophy. Laws are considered as *bad* when they do not conform to the founding premise of being a law, to realize justice and the common good (Dickson, 2009:169). When the law goes against the purpose of having a law, it results in something distorted that is not quite a law, but rather a corruption of law.

Additionally, the ACIAF Act does not uphold three out of the eight principles of good law (Fuller, 1969). It does not conform to the principle of not abusing retrospective legislation which cannot guide action but can undercut other rules (Fuller, 1969: 39). The ACIAF Act is focused on punishment without concern for limiting the conditions that enable corrupt practices. Another critical drawback is the law’s clarity, as the ACIAF Act contains unclear definitions of the phenomena it aims to tackle, i. e. “corruption” and “illegally acquired property”. Unclear definitions can obstruct enforcement and result in transgressing the internal morality of the law, namely, going against the common good by abusing the legislation for private interests. Another critical point is when judges cannot justify their decisions to sentence a man to jail and enforce a law without expressing its purpose which can lead to unjust punishments (Fuller, 1969: 131). Thus, the bad law fails to achieve its normative purpose and does not realize the values it is supposed to.

Explaining anti-corruption legislature failure

It is simplistic to infer that bad anti-corruption laws were adopted because politicians are corrupt, but it is also unreasonable to dismiss such claims. It is worth testing all explanations for the adoption of flawed anti-corruption laws. By using the corruption literature as a starting point, there are two commonly inferred explanations for ineffective policies. The first one argues politicians' lack of political will to fight this problem is due to them being corrupt or having other priorities. This idea invokes the concept of *particularism*, which is a cultural explanation, holding that there are widespread informal relationships between people eroding formal institutions (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2006; Sousa, 2009). The second explanation draws upon the unsuitable institutional design, which could result from poor choices, lack of expertise, or the will to create 'bogus institutions' (Ledeneva, 2011; Manion, 2018). Henceforth, to test these potential explanations, it is worth looking at the process of policy choice-making in the Bulgarian National Assembly. There are agency-based explanations of poor law-making which involve intra-elite disputes, strategic intra-political bargaining, civil pressure, uninformed choices, and lack of expertise. Others highlight the institutional procedures, which can structure behavior.

Lack of political will to fight corruption. Scholarship on anti-corruption policies defines lack of political will as one of the strongest reasons behind failure. The term 'political will' relates to the idea that 'effective reforms to combat corruption would need to be initiated by the very actors who are argued to benefit most from the existing, corrupt status quo' (Batory, 2012). An analysis of the anti-corruption efforts in Bulgaria shows that political will and administrative capacity were insufficient to produce tangible results, so cases of grand-scale political corruption identified by the civil society were left unaddressed by the executive and the legislative branches (CSD, 2019: 5).

The literature emphasizes the relationship between the political and oligarchic elites who re-enforce the patrimonial behavior in the public and private sectors. Bratu, Sotiropolous, and Stoyanova point out that in Bulgaria there is a 'strong political will to protect local entrepreneurs, their fortunes, and ways of doing things' (2017: 142). When the conceptualization of political will enters the realm of informality, informal decisions and personal interests drive politicians' actions towards weaker anti-corruption efforts so they maximize their personal benefits. Thus, scholars like Alina Mungiu-Pippidi (2006) and Alena Ledeneva (1998) emphasize the informal ways of decision- and policy-making marked by particularism. However, the political elite's motivations are accountable for executive and legislative inactivity, and they can also lead to overwhelming action to keep up with the changing pressing demands of international actors like the EU, IMF, UN, OECD, and civil society. Thus, Meagher explains that once the elite is corrupted, it 'will attempt to reduce the effectiveness of the legal and the judicial systems through manipulation of resource allocation and appointments to key positions' (2005: 78).

Executive-dominated legislature. The literature on corrupt law-making has been undertaken mostly by scholars of authoritarianism, where the legislature is dominated by the executive as in Russia, Mexico, Brazil, or China. As Ben Noble (2020) shows in his analysis of the Russian legislature, the legislative process is marked by intra-elite disputes and the State Duma serves as an elite battleground. Around 80% of the bills proposed by non-executive or opposition actors in Russia are drafts of executive representatives unapproved by the rest of the executive actors to become formal government initiatives (Noble and Schulmann, 2018: 64). Parliamentary systems exhibit similar patterns since party leaders usually become part of the executive because the cabinet is a product of the legislature and the ruling coalition. Hence, 'the electoral fortunes of legislators tend to be strongly associated with government performance' (Borges and Ribeiro, 2001: 3).

Moreover, as Zubek argues there is a tendency in Eastern Europe of the party-driven executive influence over the legislature. The executives dominate the legislative agenda by introducing the bulk of legislation. However, in contrast to rather authoritarian states, the democratic parliament continues to 'reshape government bills and the parliamentary committees provide a key site for finalization of drafting and coalition bargaining' (Zubek, 2008: 148). Similarly, political scientists argue that in established European democracies, parliaments play a marginal role in the creation of policies, since 'policy is created at the ministerial and cabinet levels, and then largely "rubber-stamped" by a government's support coalition' (Martin and Vanberg, 2011: 4). Martin and Vanberg (2011) show that ministers in Western Europe frequently delegate bills to their coalitional co-members with legislative powers to advocate them and facilitate their adoption. Meanwhile, it is unreasonable to underestimate the parliament, where policies undergo immense change. Thus, a fusion of powers between the executive and the legislative branches is likely to take place in parliamentary democracies where the legislature forms the governing cabinet.

The centrality of party structures in the legislature. Calise (1994) claims that parties are the place where the fusion of power takes place in parliamentary systems, where parties act as a monopoly: "The legislative and the executive branches are dependent on party organization for their electoral support, as well as for recruitment of the political class. This means that the people sitting in both governmental branches are party people in the first place, and legislative or executive officers only as a result of their party's choice." (1994: 44)

Maria Amparo Casar (1999) builds upon the dominance of the executive over the legislature and analyses their relationship to the party structures. She establishes that loyalties to the party leaders are crucial for party members' selection as deputies because they facilitate the approval of the executive's agenda. Moreover, the majority party exercises stronger control over the legislative agenda (Casar, 2013: 225). According to the procedural cartel theory developed by Cox and McCubbins (2004), parties seek to determine the agenda, but also to monopolize legislative resources. This means the majority party appoints loyal members in agenda-setting offices (i.e. committee chairs, the speakership) so they can push legislation to pass regardless of the deputies' wishes. Cheibub, Figueiredo, and Limongi (2009) argue that parties play a central role in the legislative process since loyal party members in leading procedural positions can control the agenda of the legislature while encouraging voting cohesion. Such party interests dominating the procedures and the agenda can push for legislation in favor of the aggregated party interest.

For example, a case study on the media law amendment in Croatia shows that deputies from the Socialist Democratic Party, driven by party interests, aimed to manipulate the activity of the journal *Feral Tribune*, which was critical of the leading Socialist Democratic Party at the time (Baric-Selmic et al, 2017). Parties also aggregate personal interests within a group and encourage voting cohesion. Through party structures, corrupt legislation can be adopted. Moreover, studies on parliamentary politics that emphasize party structures highlight that legislative committees can strengthen the opposition by giving it an opportunity to amend when the opposition is disciplined and cohesive (Martin and Vanberg, 2005: 103).

Informal interests vested in the legislative process. A study based on the anthropology of law has identified that particular civil, private, and political actors disproportionately influenced the creation of the Civil Society Act in Serbia by translating informal networks into official legal matters and parliamentary disputes (Mikus, 2015). Personal officeholding benefits are considered a driving force of individuals' legislative behavior. Martin and Vanberg claim that party leaders who join coalitions can serve the interests of the powerful, be it a ruling parliamentary majority or the executive:

for many professional politicians, these perks—gaining a seat at the cabinet table, or even just being a member of the governing coalition in parliament—will be tempting. They represent, after all, the achievement of the upper echelons of their profession. [...] As a result, there exists what economists typically refer to as a *moral hazard* problem in the relationship between party leaders and the remainder of the party's supporters. All have a collective interest in placing the party in a position to influence policy, which is generally enhanced by membership in the cabinet (2011, p. 11).

Nevertheless, informal personal and/or private interests, also dubbed as rent-seeking, which are greater in states with a higher degree of state capture, invoke the formal-informal conceptual nexus and link the law-making scholarship to the study of informal practices and relationships eroding the formal ones.

The legislative process as a spectacle of power

The legislative process in Bulgaria. The National Assembly has a leading role in the Bulgarian representative democracy and its institutional framework (Hristova-Valcheva, 2010). The National Assembly is the legislative power and it cooperates with other institutions, such as the Council of Ministers (CM), which has a right to legislative initiative, and the President, who is obliged to promulgate the laws and has the right of amendatory veto.⁷ Only the CM and the national representatives are allowed legislative initiatives (1991 Bulgarian Constitution, art. 87). The National Assembly assumes these powers because it represents the people as the sovereign and is supposed to express their will justly (Drumeva, 2008).

After a bill's submission to the National Assembly, the legislative process has two stages: the 'pre-floor' deliberation, and the plenary deliberation (Kanev, 2002: 173). The pre-floor deliberation takes place in the standing committees of the National Assembly and the actors submitting the bill should participate and answer the questions of the expert deputies in the committees. The preliminary discussions in the committees occur at the first and second reading. The standing committees exercise parliamentary control over the bills when they are proposed by the executive, by gathering expertise on the legislation and communicating any concerns with the executive's representatives (Nikolova, 2020: 13). The first reading can take place at more than one standing committee, but the second one is given to one specialized committee. The formation of the CACIAF was conferred to the Committee on Legal Affairs (CoLA).

The plenary sessions occur twice with two readings, following the ones in the committee. The first reading includes a general consideration of the bill, while the second deals with the details of the draft law and the written amendments of the national representatives (Drumeva, 2008). Every reading is followed by a voting procedure in the National Assembly. The vote in the plenary sessions is final, while in the committees it is advisory. If it does not pass the first reading, the bill is suspended, but if it passes the second, it becomes adopted. Legislation is adopted with a simple majority of the attending national representatives if the necessary quorum of 121 deputies in the plenary session is fulfilled. Citizens can participate in the process by submitting recommendations for amendments to the legislation in question to the National Assembly, but they are not obligatory for consideration (Atanasova, 2015: 11).

⁷ By using the amendatory veto, the president can turn the bill to the parliament with recommendations for amendment. Afterwards the parliament should reconsider the bill in a further reading.

Figure 1. The legislative process in Bulgaria

The shortcomings of the CACIAF. The ACIAF Act is the culmination of 15 years of anti-corruption efforts as it brought together all pre-existing legislation on confiscating illegal assets and identifying conflict of interest that were dispersed across multiple ministries.⁸ Under the pressure of the European Commission's Cooperation and Verification Mechanism (European Commission, 2018: 7), the anti-corruption agency was created by merging the previously existing state units. However, some of these structures were not fully compatible because the civil confiscation procedure had not been oriented towards high-ranking officials while establishing conflict of interest provisions targets such people (President Decree 274).

The new CACIAF was assigned with far-reaching special investigative powers to identify the illegal acquirement of assets, conflict of interest, disparities between assets and income that amount to more than 20,000 leva (about 10000 euros), to gather evidence, and to file cases accusing of corruption that need to be submitted to the prosecution. One of the most publicly discussed features of CACIAF is that it can start the procedure to seize illegally acquired property when there is reasonable doubt that a property has been acquired illegally, or when significant discrepancies between the declared and owned property of a person are discovered. This process of civic forfeiture cannot be revoked or reversed if a final court ruling states that the person is not guilty. Another problematic provision is that the mechanism of appointment is based on a simple majority in the National Assembly, which would favor the largest parliamentary group (European Commission, 2020).

⁸ The Commission for Confiscation of Illegally Acquired Property; the Commission for the Establishment of Property Acquired from Criminal Activity; the specialized unit in the State Agency National Security; the specialized unit of the Court Hall; the Center for Prevention and Countering of Corruption and Organized Crime to the Council of Ministers.

Moreover, the definitions of “illegally acquired property”⁹, “corruption”¹⁰, and “reasonable doubt for corruption” are imprecise and cause interpretative problems when courts make decisions. The definition of “legal sources of income” is also unrealistically limited because it includes only sources that are declared, when the legal practice has shown that undeclared sources could also be legitimate (Ivanov, 2017). Additionally, the law allows the investigation of people close to the suspect of a corrupt crime, breaching the fundamental principle that everyone is innocent until proven otherwise (Atanasov, 2019). It includes unfavorable provisions for the accused and suspected, such as shorter deadlines for the provision of evidence, fines for no compliance, rigorous investigation of close ones, no protection for signal providers, no protection of third parties, no anonymous signals, etc. It is also vested with powers similar to those of a security institution, although CACIAF can only report its findings (Ivanov, 2017). This could allow misusing power to repress opposition groups and individuals (ACFF, 2017). Implementing a powerful anti-corruption legal mechanism was imperative since Bulgaria has not shown any progress in corruption perception levels since the EU accession (CSD, 2016: 12). However, when values antithetic to good governance, such as private interest, take precedence over the interest of society, ‘institutional checks and balances, and effective oversight of bureaucrats by elected officials can be rendered meaningless’ (Johnston, 1999: 4). These shortcomings allowed the mismanagement of the anti-corruption policy implementation and a potential abuse of power. Such institutions representative of bad governance in Bulgaria have been dubbed as ‘bat institutions’ (*institutsiya buhalka*) (Paunova, 2020).

The National Assembly debate and the anti-corruption law, October 2017 – January 2018. Since GERB won its first majority in parliament in 2009 and continued to dominate the legislature almost until 2021, their priorities were oriented towards infrastructure projects and European integration. Throughout GERB’s first two terms, new integrity-controlling institutions were established, such as the civic forfeiture and conflict of interest commissions (CIAF and CECI), while the creation of an anti-corruption agency was envisaged in the 2015-2020 Strategy for Combatting Corruption. However, the most important function of GERB’s electorate was to counterbalance the reformed communists of BSP and their Russophile attitudes. Throughout this entire period, BSP was the opposition to GERB, and the ruling coalitions. The discourse of both parties revolved around their mutual competition, despite them successfully reaching a compromise numerous times. The debate regarding CACIAF is not an exception. The rhetoric of both parties’ spokespeople was embedded with party squabbles. Nevertheless, GERB engaged in state capture, facilitated by their control of both the legislature and the executive. As the leading party, GERB dominated the decision-making process within the ruling coalitions. Thus, ministerial positions were filled with loyal party people. Similar to Italy, the institutional framework of Bulgaria’s parliamentary democracy enables a fusion of powers through which a dominating party can monopolize the government process (Calise, 1994, p. 446). For example, state enterprises such as the Bulgarian Energy Holding, Maritza Iztok, and crucial institutions such as the Agency for Competition Protection and the General Prosecution were chaired by people loyal to the party structure (Veselinova, 2021). Kanev explains that:

⁹ Illegally acquired property is defined as: ‘Property according to Art 1 and 2 is considered property that has not been acquired through established lawful means.’ (ACIAF Act, art. 5)

¹⁰ Corruption is defined as: ‘Corruption within the meaning of this law shall exist, where as a result of the occupied high public position, the person abuses his power, violates or fails to perform official obligations in view to direct, or indirect retrieving of unreasonable material or intangible benefits for themselves or for other persons’. (ACIAF Act, art. 3)

One of the features permanently eroding the democratic character of Bulgarian politics is the contradiction between the consensual substance of the constitution and the "majority *politicking*" of actual politics. Each political party winning elections opts for centralization of power and for non-cooperative and exclusive politics as it tries to take advantage of its governmental status for personal and party ends. Pure majority rule replaces consensus in the decision-making process; (2002: 174).

Hence, it is not a surprise that citizens' trust in parliament decreased to 5% in 2013 (Dainov, 2013: 128-129). But it was only in the 2017 parliamentary elections the idea for an anti-corruption agency entered the political discourse, via the electoral campaigns of the urban liberal parties – New Republic and Yes, Bulgaria. They emphasized the need for an institution modeled according to the Romanian agency and eulogized the successful incarcerations of corrupt Romanian ministers. Although these parties failed to enter the National Assembly in 2017, their idea echoed in the new parliament, and creating a comprehensive anti-corruption mechanism became a top priority. Although the recommendations of the EC were outlined as a pretext for the ACIAF bill (Tsacheva, NA Deb 25 October 2017), this was not the first time EU institutions called for such an initiative. The timing of the bill was not motivated solely by external influence. It rather shows that there was a strategic calculation on behalf of the ruling elite, to use their first-mover advantage (i.e. the right of the executive to initiate bills) to propose their version of such legislation before someone else does so. Moreover, GERB would benefit from the popularity stemming from this initiative also European-wise since the Bulgarian presidency of the EU began in January, when the bill was adopted.

The design of the legislation submitted by the CM on the 6th of October was inspired by the bill submitted in 2015 by Kuneva because these two bills are very similar as both unite the same already existing integrity state structures (Vesselinova, 2017). Although Tsetska Tsacheva, the justice minister at the time, claimed that the legislation was approved by the Venice Commission (CoLA Deb 19 October 2017), the fact that the 2015 text was used points to the limited research and expertise to develop a new version. The point of the draft law was to satisfy the recommendations of the EC by establishing cooperation procedures with the rest of the investigating and prosecuting authorities but without introducing new tools for combatting corruption (Kashamov, 2017). The rest of the parties did not have experience in such matters as shown by the parliamentary debates. Nonetheless, BSP submitted an alternative draft law for the establishment of a state agency called "Anticorruption". BSP also lacked knowledge in the matter, but they asked the Administrative Court for help in drafting the bill named Countering Corruption Among High-ranking Public Officials Bill.

The desire to show power was critical in GERB's approach to the debates. Considering their majority and unanimous support from OP and DPS, the behavior of the majority expressed their expectation that the law would pass unhindered, rendering the opposition meaningless. This displayed their perception of the debate as a formality without any constructive purpose. The cooperation between the executive and the legislative majority of GERB was notable throughout the debates since GERB advocated the bill and did not criticize it. It appeared that the executive and the ruling coalition had aggregated interests and expressed a cohesive relationship. Cohesiveness should be understood as unanimous voting and also as a certain consensus in values and attitudes (Jensen, 2000: 211). The main actors in the debates were GERB and BSP, while DPS proposed most amendments. Considering that 'the legislative process bolsters the opportunities of the opposition parties to wield influence over the direction of public policy' (Martin and Vanberg, 2005: 103), BSP attempted to use the committees and the plenary sessions to discredit the executive's bill, but without much success. OP played a marginal role, while *Volya* had no notable participation. Throughout the debates, the critiques were oriented toward party units instead of individual members. Thus, deputies employed a party approach,

emphasizing the importance of intra-party consolidation. Alongside their largely unanimous voting, the legislative process shows that party structures are crucial in the Bulgarian legislative system and suggests that individuals reached compromises over their private interests prior to the public debate, behind closed doors.

Competing anti-corruption legislations. After both drafts were submitted, they passed the first reading in the standing committees on Legal Affairs (CoLA), on Regional Politics, Development and Local Self-Governance and on Countering Corruption, and on Conflict of Interest and Parliamentary Ethics. The executive bill was voted to proceed to a hearing in the National Assembly while the BSP bill was voted for suspension but did not pass.¹¹ Although the total number of CoLA members is 31, only 21 were present during the first discussion and the voting figures mirrored the composition of the committee with 7 representatives from BSP supporting their bill, and the rest endorsing the executive one. GERB's most active representative, Daniel Kirilov, pointed out that his party co-members in the committee did not fulfill their agenda-setting purpose and should not have allowed the BSP bill to proceed (NA Deb 25 October 2017; NA Deb 22 December 2017). By applying the typology of Schlessinger for legislative behavior according to office-seeking ambitions, Daniel Kirilov represents the progressive ambition to 'attain an office more important than the one he now seeks or is holding' (Schlessinger, 1996: 10).¹² Based on the number of speeches and amendments, he was the most active MP on the floor.

Bargaining in the CoLA as a specialized standing committee for this issue took place on October 19th, December 6th and 7th, and January 10th. The plenary discussions took place on October 25th, and 14, 15, 22 December 14th, 15th, 22nd, and January 12th. The recordings are published on the website of the National Assembly. The debate was unusually prolonged due to the Presidential veto. The critical points discussed were the nature of the law, the civic forfeiture procedure, the appointment mechanism, the anonymity of signals, and the special investigatory powers. The representatives of the executive were active in the sessions of CoLA but not in the National Assembly. The external stakeholders' behavior was similarly inert, despite attending only the second reading in the standing committee. The anti-corruption discourse became a battleground between GERB and BSP mainly used for publicity. However, significant changes in Bulgarian legislation were not installed and this gesture of political will to fight corruption was perceived as rather simulated (Veselinova, 2017).

GERB representative and Justice Minister Tsetska Tsacheva opened the plenary debate by elaborating that the executive bill aimed at uniting the existing anti-corruption and integrity authorities, which would proceed to function, while collaborating more effectively (NA Deb 25 October 2017). She stated that according to the bill, the chairperson and the commission members would be elected by a simple majority in the National Assembly. The appointment mechanism was the most discussed subject. The main critique of BSP was that a simple majority in this National Assembly equaled the ruling coalition dominated by GERB. Hence, it would facilitate the abuse of power because they will appoint loyal people. BSP member Krum Zarkov accused GERB of such power abuse by giving as an example the chairman of CIAF at the time, Plamen Georgiev, who was sitting in office besides the fact that his mandate was prolonged because of his loyalty to GERB (NA Deb 25 October 2017). To promote the executive bill, GERB member Tsvetan Tsvetanov stated that initially the appointment mechanism in the bill was vested in the cabinet. However, the cabinet foresaw the criticism for potential conflict

¹¹ The executive bill received 14 in favor and 7 against, while the BSP bill received 7 in favor and 14 abstained.

¹² After the *Apartmentgate* scandal, Tsetska Tsacheva resigned from being the Minister of Justice and Daniel Kirilov was appointed in her place (OffNews, 2019).

of interest and made the new CACIAF more plural, by outlining the National Assembly as the appointing body. Nevertheless, BSP members continually claimed that it would create conflicts of interest and that the CACIAF would never be independent and investigate its bosses (NA Deb 22 December 2017).¹³

It is reasonable to suggest that BSP's bill was a tactic for publicity. Its submission to parliament was fortuitous because it had been expected that compromises would be achieved at earlier open discussions between parliamentary groups. Moreover, it was not a sustainable alternative for institutional design, because the draft law was only 24 pages long¹⁴ and lacked significant information for the law to pass, as indicated by GERB: the necessary budget, the envisioned staff, the procedure of appointment of staff on all levels, and other minor details are all inconclusive. Therefore, it was clear that this bill was unadoptable. GERB representatives emphasized the attributes of their bill in juxtaposition to BSP's. The major shortcoming of BSP's bill was considered to be the appointment mechanism, which was problematic because it bestowed these powers to the president.

This move by BSP was strategically calculated because President Rumen Radev was framed as the antagonist in GERB's narrative, despite his wide support by the public.¹⁵ It was clear that each party in the National Assembly would vote against any type of empowerment of the president, despite the presidential figure's ability to bring plurality. By provoking a rejection to a more pluralist framework involving different structures such as both the president and the parliament, BSP aimed to show to the public that the other parties have personal interests to control the checks and balances and are unwilling to dispute it. Nonetheless, GERB representative Dimitar Lazarov called the bill 'an idea project' and rejected it as an alternative without hesitation (NA Deb 25 October 2017). The ruling party's attitude also shows that GERB's plan was not to make compromises but to put through their project.

The 'idea project' was more rigid and innovative than the executive one, which united existing structures that failed to show substantial results. BSP representatives, such as Krum Zarkov and Pencho Milkov, argued the merger would not lead to progress and considered it unreasonable to think old institutions would suddenly start to be effective, given that the proposed legislation changes nearly nothing about their procedures and powers (NA Deb 25 October 2017). BSP deputy Todor Baichev continued the argument by inferring that this body will not prosecute anyone guilty of major corruption, especially since the highest levels of power are in the cabinet, which would indirectly appoint the members of the commission through the network of GERB (NA Deb 25 October 2017). Thus, the body could become an instrument for repression with its special power to confiscate illegally acquired property despite the lack of precision in the procedure.

The lack of knowledge on the matter was also an issue within the debates, together with the lack of a strong opinion by DPS, OP, and *Volya*. An interesting position on the matter of where corruption is located in Bulgarian society was taken by the small populist party *Volya* and its leader, Vesselin Mareshki, who claimed that both bills are the same and are produced by the hands of corruption. He stated that the echelons that need to be investigated abruptly are in the cabinet (NA Deb 25 October 2017). In line with his anti-establishment rhetoric, he said he will not support any of the bills. Nevertheless, *Volya* members voted in favor of the executive bill. Additionally, United Patriots had a distinct view from the rest. They claimed that corruption is not a devastating problem, and it is

¹³ The most vocal BSP members were Krum Zarkov, Filip Popov, Yavor Bozhankov, Todor Baichev, and Pencho Milkov.

¹⁴ In comparison to the executive bill which was 97 pages.

¹⁵ President Rumen Radev, independent but endorsed by BSP, won against the GERB candidate Tsetska Tsacheva with 58%.

only presented as such by the European institutions (NA Deb 25 October 2017; NA Deb 12 January 2018). Therefore, such a body is unnecessary. Criticism against the approach of the EU was undertaken by DPS representative Yordan Tzonev, who claimed that the EU bodies have no expertise in such measures since there is no other member country besides Romania that has such a body. Therefore, the European criticism of the ineffectiveness of the existing legislation, echoed by BSP, is irrelevant, because they lack experience. This claim exposed the lack of expertise on the issue because many EU member states have an anti-corruption institution.¹⁶ In other words, none of the deputies in the parliament knew anti-corruption mechanisms, which would clearly lead to uninformed decisions.

From the Anti-Corruption Bill to the Anti-Corruption Act. The second reading focused solely on the executive bill since BSP's bill did not pass. The presumption of the second voting procedure is that all parties contribute to the tailoring of the bill according to each party's and/or individual representative's agenda, interests, and expertise. Representatives of the civil society also partook in CoLA.¹⁷ Additionally, external stakeholders submitted criticism of the executive bill and recommendations as public statements before the second vote, which were dismissed by the parliamentary majority but taken into account by the opposition.¹⁸ The final version of the bill was not very different from the initial one with few minor changes related to wording.

Table 1. Amendment adoption by party and type of change in the second voting in the Committee on Legal Questions (CoLA Rep, 11 December 2017).

Party	Total amendment suggestions	Adopted amendments	Amendments voted against	Withdrawn proposed amendment	Substantial change of meaning	Minor change/ wording
GERB	13	12	0	1	2	11
BSP	3	0	3	0	0	3
DPS	39	4	25	11	21	18
UP	23	3	15	4	8	15
Volya	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	78	19	41	16	31	46

Table 1 represents the distribution of amendments by party and their adoption ratio. The table offers two categories based on the nature of the amendments proposed. Drawing upon the concept of 'comprehensive changes' within constitutional amendments in constitutional theory (Manfredi and Lusztig, 1998: 380), a legislative amendment is considered substantial when it alters the essence of the legislation or the institutional framework so that it modifies the underlying concepts of the bill and the power equilibrium between the public and the governmental actors. Alternatively, minor changes are conceptualized as 'incremental constitutional changes' because they modify discrete aspects without changing the expected outcome of the legislation. Minor amendments and changes in wording are epistemologically similar since they would not lead to changes in the outcomes.

¹⁶ Italy, France, Spain, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Latvia, Poland, Croatia.

¹⁷ Civil society structures were represented such as: Bulgarian Institute for Law Initiatives, Access to Information Programme, Institute for Market Economics, Anti-Corruption Fund Foundation, Civil Society Experts Association, National Movement for Bulgarian Citizens (CoLA Protocol No. 27, 6 Dec 2017)

¹⁸ The Supreme Bar Association, the Anti-Corruption Fund Foundation, Former Minister of Justice and chairman of Yes Bulgaria party – Hristo Ivanov, Chamber of Surveyors in Bulgaria.

The clear trend of voting unanimously across party lines was notable in all readings, and amendments were largely suggested by party fractions instead of individual representatives. Only up to 4 members of GERB, DPS, OP, and *Volya* voted against the party line. Since these votes were cast by different people, there was nobody with a concrete anti-bill or anti-executive agenda. The maintenance of a cohesive voting block was significant for the parties to win ‘the parliamentary game’ (Bowler et al, 1999: 3). BSP’s strategy was distinctive, with a single member proposing the amendments,¹⁹ while the rest of the party performed a boycott by only criticizing the bill without offering any formal proposals. BSP was the most undisciplined party, with several members voting differently from the rest of their group on several issues and not voting on others. Some of BSP’s members who voted differently from the party line were the same who supported the appointment of Sotir Tsatsarov as the head of CACIAF.²⁰ There is a clear conflict of interest since he used to hold the controversial role of general prosecutor before heading the CACIAF.²¹ These voting patterns reflected the intra-party disputes in BSP, which weakened their position against the bill and did not allow them to put more pressure on the rest of the deputies.

Table 2. Amendment adoption by party and type of change in the second voting in the Plenary Session (NA Deb 14 December 2017; NA Deb 15 December 2017; NA Deb 22 December 2017).

Party	Total amendment suggestions	Adopted amendments	Substantial change of meaning	Minor change/ wording
GERB	23	23	2	21
BSP	4	0	1	3
DPS	31	2	14	17
UP	9	3	4	5
Volya	0	0	0	0
Total	67	25	21	46

The dominance of the executive was unequivocal since people loyal to the cabinet but without interest in the corruption issue itself dominated the legislature, meaning they spoke without addressing the specifics of the bill. Despite heated debates on some provisions, the amendments received limited support. The nature of the executive bill was debated by BSP members starting from their concerns regarding the use of special investigatory powers as described in Chapter 9 ‘Counteracting corruption by revealing activities of individuals in high public offices’. The proposal of DPS advocated by Ihsan Hakka in the Plenary Session was to erase the whole Chapter 9, because it is unreasonable for the agency to use special-investigatory powers which are vested only in security-related institutions, especially since CACIAF reports cannot be taken as evidence but only as accusation. Consequently, the motives for having such powers are insufficient and would not lead to ‘a

¹⁹ The BSP member, Ivan Valentinov Ivanov, proposed three amendments, but he did not vote on any amendment including his own.

²⁰ The BSP members who voted in favor or did not vote despite attending (inactive support) during the CACIAF debate and the Tsatsarov appointment are: Ivan Valentinov Ivanov, Georgi Andreev, Dimitar Georgiev, Chavdar Velinov, Petar Kanev, Toma Tomov, Bogdan Botsev, Ivan Ibrishimov, Bogdan Botsev, Georgi Tarnovaliiski, Nikolai Penev, Valeri Zhablyanov.

²¹ For more information on the general prosecution in Bulgaria see Transparency International Bulgaria. 2004. *Prosecution – Condition and Legislative Problems*, Sofia.

reciprocated result' (NA Deb 20 December 2017). Moreover, the surveillance of individuals for suspicion of administrative and civil offenses and the storage of incriminating material are against the Bulgarian constitution, as well as the storage of incriminating material (CoLA Deb 7 December 2017). Alexander Kashamov, a representative of the civil organization 'Access to Information' program, endorsed the DPS proposal by arguing that Bulgarian authorities abuse their power to investigate, and the country was sued several times in the European Court of Human Rights for disproportional interference in someone's private life and correspondence (CoLA Deb 7 December 2017). BSP representatives Krum Zarkov and Valery Zhablyanov echoed these arguments, but also added that without this provision the bill would be rendered meaningless since this is the only part that provides an addendum to the existing legislation, and it is related to tackling corruption (CoLa Deb 7 December 2017; NA Deb 22 December 2017). The argument in favor of this provision by Deputy Minister of Justice Evgeni Stoyanov stated that with these special-investigatory powers, the agency would be fully independent since it would not need to collaborate with the State Agency National Security (CoLA Deb 7 December 2017). The amendment received only 11 votes in favor out of 105 and it did not pass.²²

While the structure of GERB allowed the monopolization over the legislature and the executive by employing loyal party members and encouraging cohesion, OP and DPS showed a subservient attitude to the center of power and resource distribution – the executive. The collaboration between DPS, OP, and the executive in showing support for the most repressive provision of the ACIAF Act suggests their favoritism not so much for the majority party, but for the executive. Thus, considering that knowledge and stance on the issue were not in abundance, the smaller parties chose to strengthen their own positions by playing along with the powerful decision-makers. This subservient attitude was present during the discussion of the controversial practice of illegal asset forfeiture. Krum Zarkov, from BSP, explained that the so-called procedure of civil forfeiture was a subject of many contradictions and it engendered interpretative issues in court (NA Deb 14 December 2017). Todor Baichev claimed that the term "illegally acquired assets" was fundamentally flawed because if the procedure of transferring property was illegal then the deal is invalid, and the accused person does not own this property (NA Deb 14 December 2017). On the other hand, Hamid Hamid claimed that the term was clear enough for the court (CoLA Deb 7 December 2017). His statements in defense of the definition were backed by Plamen Georgiev (CIAF chairman)²³ and Deputy Minister of Justice Evgeni Stoyanov. Additionally, a representative of the official coalitional partner OP - Hristiyan Mitev, joined Hamid and Georgiev in defending the most dubious parts, concerning the civil confiscation on the presumption that illegally acquired assets exist regardless of the final ruling of the court on the case.

The lack of knowledge on anti-corruption institutional design was notable in the discussion of another contentious issue concerning the protection of the signal providers. DPS member Hamid called for an addendum to the bill that would hold the signal providers responsible in case of misleading signals, which was supported throughout the debates by OP representative Hristiyan Mitev. His argument was based upon the possibility that a fake signal could destroy the reputation of someone in case there is a following media attention, consequently, the signal provider should be considered responsible (NA Deb 15 December 2017). This amendment received the support of BSP member Filip

²² These votes included all the attending deputies from DPS, three from BSP, 1 from GERB and 1 from OP.

²³ Plamen Georgiev became the first chairman of the CACIAF via his already expired mandate from the CIAF as he was transferred as the chairman after the merger of the existing state structures. After the *Apartmentgate* scandal in which Georgiev also possessed illegal property, he was transferred in 2019 as Consul in Valencia of the Bulgarian Diplomatic Mission in Spain.

Popov, who argued that if signal provision is not restricted, the mechanism will spark a culture of slandering (NA Deb 14 December 2017). However, such claims are contradictory to recent anti-corruption recommendations for the protection of whistle-blowers. This also suggests that neither of the deputies had updated knowledge of anti-corruption institutional design and the importance of anonymous signals or electronic platforms for signal submission as suggested by the statement of Hristo Ivanov (2017). The issue was a major topic during the session of the committee, where the representatives of the Anti-Corruption Fund Foundation and the Access to Information Program, suggested that such signals should be anonymous and/or provide protection for whistle-blowers (CoLA Deb 6 December 2017). It is interesting to note that the concerns of all debaters are related to the potential repressive character of the institution, instead of good anti-corruption practices. On this issue, the opposition and the smaller parties joined forces and struck down Article 49 which protected the signal providers. It is also important to note that only Daniel Kirilov stood up against his opponents and claimed that his parliamentary group would continue to endorse the bill unequivocally (NA Deb 15 December 2017). This statement publicly exemplified the subservience of the parliamentary group to the executive, suggesting their intra-party consolidated cohesion on their public behavior and their strongly aggregated interests with the executive.

The lack of will to improve the bill and to introduce a more comprehensive anti-corruption mechanism was most obvious in the reading after the presidential veto. The motives of the veto were presented but without leading to any changes. The session was also an exhibit of GERB's procedural control that undermined their opponents. The reading was scheduled during the parliamentary holiday and the notice was given only one day in advance. One day is typically insufficient for the opposition to discipline its members, to develop a strategy and to prepare the necessary research. The short notice period hindered the participation of the deputies, especially the ones from BSP who could prolong the debate. In fact, only 17 deputies managed to attend the committee (CoLA Deb 10 January 2018).

Conclusion

This analysis of the legislative process in Bulgaria shows that agency and structure are congruent. Individuals can erode group actions and strategies, while consolidated units appear more influential and can devour other individuals, groups, and networks. Moreover, cohesive groups can also dominate the institutional enablers of influencing legislation, which is predisposed by the institutional framework that allows a certain degree of fusion of powers despite their constitutionally established division.

The legislative process in Bulgaria shows that party structures are crucial for the policy and law-making process. GERB's domination over the pre-floor and plenary sessions put them in a position of being the only political group that could easily amend the law and tweak it according to their preferences and expertise. Moreover, the numerical dominance of GERB allowed them not to compromise with anyone while the other parties compromised with them on many occasions. The party discipline and cohesion across GERB, OP, and DPS facilitated the approbation of a *bad* law that would endanger the Bulgarian democracy because of its repression potential. None of these groups had statements contradictory to the party line. In contrast, the lack of discipline among BSP members hindered their influence over the legislation despite their party strategy of discrediting the bill and its supporters, considering that only a heterogeneous and unified opposition' can aspire to control outcomes (Dios, 1999: 143).

The executive played a twofold role. On one hand, its intermingling with the network of GERB was evident, since the behavior of GERB deputies consisted of unequivocally backing the bill and

proposing cosmetic changes so that the bill would pass in a form as similar to the initial one as possible. The Bulgarian legislative process exhibited centralized leadership in the hands of a political party, conforming to the concept of partocracy (Ibraimllari, 2017: 73). Due to the powers of the ruling coalition to form a cabinet by appointing loyal people in the governing process, the legislature-dominating party can control the executive. Hence, the ACIAF bill could be seen as originating as much from the executive as from GERB. On the other hand, the executive appeared as an influential player for the smaller parties of OP, DPS, and *Volya*, who favored the ministers and never inserted a critique on the government in their rhetoric in contrast to their hostile attitude to other parties. They did not exert substantial pressure in terms of their amendments and defined the debates as “constructive” despite that nearly none of their suggestions were adopted (NA Deb 12 January 2018). Their static office-seeking interest to keep their relatively influential position in the legislature took precedence over their insufficient knowledge and weak stance on the matter (Herrick and Moore, 1993: 765), which guided them to support not the law in particular, but the legislative initiative of the executive. The discourse in the legislature contains a strict conceptual division between party structures and the executive despite their close links in reality. BSP similarly, despite its fierce anti-GERB discourse, endorsed many of the practices of the cabinet.²⁴ Thus, all the rest of the parties appeared as subservient to the executive as the main actor of power and resource distribution.

Finally, the institutional framework of the legislature allows the domination of certain actors over others. The appointment mechanism for Committee chairs and Spokespeople favoring the dominating party allows the capture of the formal procedures, and the manipulation of the discussions and agenda-setting, which ‘brings about the policy outcomes preferred by the capturing group’ (Bendor and Moe, 1986: 1190). Despite the committees being expert units that are supposed to facilitate compromise between parties based on knowledge and expertise (Olson and Norton, 1996: 11), in contrast to the plenary session where the debate is political and between the agendas of political groups, the readings in the specialized committees were also converted into a scene for party squabbles regardless of the participation of external actors. This shows that party ambitions were more important for the legislators than the issue of corruption. Thus, political will continued to be *de facto* absent from Bulgarian political life, despite the inclusion of anti-corruption in the parliamentary and executive agenda.

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²⁴ The work of the rest of the integrity agencies and the prosecution was applauded despite the BSP arguments that they should not be merged into one institution.

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